

ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND SCHOOL CUSTOM PRACTICES OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract. The study determined the extent of organizational culture and the extent of school custom practices of public elementary school teachers. This study employed non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing descriptive-correlation method. Validated questionnaire and Universal sampling procedure were utilized considering the minimal number of teachers in the research locale. One hundred twenty (120) public elementary school teachers were the respondents of the study. Using mean, pearson-r, and regression analysis, the findings revealed that the extent of organizational culture was extensive while the extent of school custom practices of public elementary school teachers was also extensive. Moreover, the overall results disclosed that indicators for the organizational culture have a strong positive correlation to the school custom practices of public elementary school teachers. Further, results from the regression analysis revealed the following have a strong influence of organizational culture on school custom practices of public elementary school teachers: Leadership, Teamwork, and Adaptability. It was suggested that a sustainable organizational culture and application of its practices, implementing the three aspects of organizational culture. It was highly recommended to promote better school performance. It was also recommended secure and sustain better school leadership, management, and governance, participation of teachers is anticipated.

KEY WORDS

1. Organizational culture,. 2. school custom practices. 3. Adaptability.

1. Introduction

A school is an organization because it is a place where formal education takes place. This implies that a social framework is composed of bunches of individuals association with one another in arrange to realize both school and person objectives. In this respect, a school must be a secured and organized place where a clear set of common rules and school teach are in arrange. The school must be steady where learners and instructors can center on learning and educating separately. For case, instructors must have a staff room where they can get ready their work some time recently a lesson, and students must have command structure, bureaucracy is the chain of organization that keeps up arrange and makes a chain of command conceivable. Each specialist tends to climb to his level of uncouthness in a progression. School culture is considered a framework of implications that impact each viewpoint of the school counting school viability. Instructive education must provide quality instruction to prepare the understud-

ies for the long run era. As such, schools offer an environment where students can learn the desired skills and information. A school's organizational culture provides a sense of identity, promotes achievement orientation, helps shape standards and patterns of behavior, creates distinct ways of doing things, and determines direction for future growth. Organizational or school culture has both positive and negative function. An organization's culture, one of the most important things that any leader can attend to, is rooted in the human issues of individuals' and teams' behavior, habits, and mindsets. It can be deliberately leveraged to great effect to guide behavior and decision-making to align with policies. It can influence the work behavior and attitudes of school personnel increasing their loyalty and commitment optimizing their performance to achieve their goals as they collaborate with each other.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research methods which give direction in this investigation. It includes the research design, research respondents of the study, research instrument and the data gathering procedures.

2.1. Research Design—This study used the non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing correlational method. According to Depra (2022), descriptive correlational method is used to determine the relationship between two or more variables and to ascertain their relationship. More to the point, Swart (2018) emphasizes that this method is used since the study provides a description of individuals and aims to explain the nature of the data. This study is descriptive in nature since it assesses the organizational culture and school custom practices of public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City. This is correlational since organizational culture and school custom practice of public elementary school teachers.

2.2. Research Respondents—This study was conducted in seven (7) schools of Maa District, Division of Davao City. The respondents were composed of 120-selected teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City. They have been in the service for at least five to ten years teaching experiences in the Department of Education (DepED) and have said something on the organizational culture and school custom practices of public elementary school teachers.

Random sampling technique were employed in this study. However, Langub Elementary School and Magtuod Elementary School with 100 percent of respondents were involved. For the rest of the schools, fifty percent were given the questionnaires. The schools were equidistantly located in the whole district, which can be reached by means of land transportation facilities. The environment is conducive to educational research.

2.3. Research Instrument—This study adapted a questionnaire on organizational culture and was patterned by the researcher from the Organizational Theory of Culture of Schein (1980) as cited by Gudoy (2022). He believed organizations developed a culture over time as employees experienced various changes, adapted to the external environment, and solved organizational problems. This is supported by Theory of Practice Bourdieu's (1977) as cited by Andal (2021). This theory emphasizes that an individual's everyday practices are not always explicit and mediated by language, but instead an individual's everyday practices are often tacit and embodied. The connection between practice and theory is important as it demonstrates your ability to use evidence to

increase your understanding of key concepts, justify your decision making, and inform future practice. The questionnaire was modified mainly through the researcher’s preferences to suit the needs of the study. The adapted questionnaire was validated by the experts from the DepEd-Division of Davao City. Validity of the instrument ensured through expert’s opinions and pilot testing. To ensure the reliability of the instrument, a pilot test conducted through calculating the value of Cronbach’s Alpha with the obtained values of 0.070. The questionnaire was divided into two (2) parts, namely: organizational culture and school custom practice of public elementary school teachers. Hence, the Cronbach’s value of the construct has met

the minimum reliability of 0.796, it means that the measures used are consistent enough for the study. In terms of instrument’s face validity, the items were modified to suit the purpose of this study and were validated by experts. The questionnaire was presented to the adviser for comments, corrections, and suggestions. Part 1 of the questionnaire contained the items organizational culture with the following: leadership, teamwork, and adaptability. Part 2 pertained to the school custom practices namely: school goal, supportive and caring environment; and curriculum and evaluation. The perceptions of the respondents among the Maa District teachers were based on the following Five-point Likert rating scales:

Range, Descriptive Equivalent, Interpretation

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very Extensive	Organizational culture is always evident.
3.40-4.19	Extensive	Organizational culture is oftentimes evident.
2.60-3.39	Moderately Extensive	Organizational culture is sometimes evident.
1.80-2.59	Less Extensive	Organizational culture is rarely evident.
1.00-1.79	Not Extensive	Organizational culture is not evident.

Range, Descriptive Equivalent, Interpretation

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very Extensive	School custom practices are always evident.
3.40-4.19	Extensive	School custom practices are oftentimes evident.
2.60-3.39	Moderately Extensive	School custom practices are sometimes evident.
1.80-2.59	Less Extensive	School custom practices are rarely evident.
1.00-1.79	Not Extensive	School heads performance are not evident.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure—*

The steps followed in the conduct of the study were: 1. Permission to conduct study. The researcher wrote a letter asking permission from the Dean of Graduate School to conduct this research study. The researcher secured a permit to conduct the study from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Davao City through channels to the Office of the Public Schools District Supervisor (PSDS) of the different schools. 2. Distribution and retrieval of questionnaires. Upon approval of the permit to conduct the study, the sets of questionnaires were sent to the respondents via google forms and through email-add of the school heads and teachers. The questionnaires were retrieved right after the respondents were through answering the questions and sent them back through researcher's email-add or messenger. 3. Collection and statistical treat-

ment of data. The data was collected during the Corona Virus Pandemic (COVID-19) time; therefore, the collection of data was based on the protocols set by the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) standards. It was a task force organized by the executive of the Philippine government to respond to affairs concerning emerging infectious diseases in the Philippine which was convened in January 2020. The collection of data was conducted following the protocols of IATF to avoid being contaminated and infected by COVID-19. For some participants who missed answering the questionnaire, the video call, via messenger, viber, zoom or goggle meet were used to gather the data or responses of the participants. These were submitted to the statistician for analysis. The researcher together with the statistician tabulated the data, analyzed and subject them for statistical analysis.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools were used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in this study. Mean. It was used to determine the extent of organizational culture of public elementary school in Maa District, Division of Davao City. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson-r). This statistical tool was used in determining the

significant of organizational culture and school custom practices of public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City. Multiple Linear Regression. This was utilized to determine the significant of organizational culture influence school custom practices of public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City.

3. Results and Discussion

Presented in this chapter were the results of the data gathered. Two sets of research were employed to determine the extent of organizational culture and school custom practices of public elementary school teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City. The discussion of the results and interpretations were presented accordingly based on the statement of the problems. Presentation of the interpretation was arranged according to the sub-headings: The extent of organizational culture in terms of leadership, teamwork, and adaptability; the extent of school custom practices of public elementary school teachers in terms of school goals, supportive and caring environment, and curriculum and evaluation; and which of the factors of organizational culture significantly influence the school custom practices of public elementary school teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City.

Summary on the Extent of Organizational Culture. Presented in table 1 shows the summary on the extent of organizational culture of public elementary school teachers. The indicator with highest mean is self-assessment (3.98), interpreted as extensive. It is then followed by teamwork has a mean of (3.67) also identified as extensive. Lastly, adaptability has the least mean of (3.57) described as extensive. With an overall generated mean of (3.74) or extensive,

therefore, the summary on the organizational culture of public elementary school was extensive as perceived by the teachers. This means that organizations employees have clear spelt out work ethics, are like-minded and hold similar beliefs and values, guided by values of consistency, adaptability, and effective communication system, gives employees a sense of identity which increases their commitment to work and ultimately leads to better performance.

Table 1. Summary on the Extent of Organizational Culture

No	Statements	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Leadership	3.89	Extensive
2	Teamwork	3.67	Extensive
3	Adaptability	3.57	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.71	Extensive

It can be gathered from the table that job leadership, teamwork, and adaptability were extensive. Adaptability was the least among the indicators of organizational culture. Successful organization have a strong sense of goals and direction that provides a vision of how the firm focused on the future and establishes organizational goals and strategic objectives (Hanci-Donmez Karacay, 2019). Organizations are also more effective when their cultures are "strong, "meaning they are consistent, well-

coordinated, and well-integrated. School leaders and supporters are good at establishing an agreement even when there are divergent points of view because their behavior is anchored in a set of core beliefs (Nguyen, Nguyen Sila, 2019). Executives, school administrators, and staff are dedicated to their works and believe they have a stake in the organization. People at all levels feel more involved when they have a say in choices that affect them and when their job is closely linked to the organization's goals.

Summary on the Extent of School Custom Practices. Presented in table 2 shows the summary extent of school custom practices of public elementary school teachers. The indicator with highest mean is school goals with a mean of (4.01), interpreted as extensive. It is then followed by curriculum and evaluation has a mean of (3.87) identified as extensive. Lastly, supportive and caring environment has the least mean of (3.84) described as extensive. With an over-

all generated mean of (3.91) or high, therefore, the summary extent of school custom practices of public elementary school was extensive as perceived by the teachers. This implies that the outcomes of schools have a strong relationship with the nature of school culture (i.e., visions, missions, and values), which emanate from the existing society, i.e., ideas, policies, and rules and regulations of the governing bodies.

Table 2. Summary on the Extent of School Custom Practices

No	Statements	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	School Goals	4.01	Extensive
2	Supportive and Caring Environment	3.84	Extensive
3	Curriculum and Evaluation	3.87	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.91	Extensive

It can be garnered from the table that school goals, supportive and caring environment, and curriculum and evaluation were extensive demonstrated by public elementary school teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City. Mostly, school culture is broadly studied like school as an organization. However, this perspective more focused on managerial aspects of school culture. According to Colenso (2000) as mentioned by Noot’s (2021), characteristics of an organization are; processes, structure, strategy, people and hierarchy. While looking at these characteristics of an organization, schools have procedures to run different programs in schools. Schools have different processes to accomplish different tasks. School culture is considered a framework of implications that impact each viewpoint of the school counting school viability. Instructive education must provide quality instruction to prepare the understudies for the long run era. As such, schools offer an environment where students can learn the desired skills and information. Each organization has diverse characteristics based on its reason and mission. Moreover, each school incorporates a one-of-a kind culture. The school culture can give the most excellent environment for the instructing and learning programs and interface the staff with the school (Dogan, 2015). The school culture is one of the factors which can impact school effectiveness. Similarly, Mart (2013) disclosed that commitment is an essential element of successful teaching. Committed teachers are concerned with the development

of their learners and they profoundly struggle with how to keep learners’ learning. They cultivate students’ curiosity and interest in learning. Showing commitment to learner learning can be an important factor in motivating learners. Committed teachers recognize and endeavor to fulfill their responsibilities to their students. The degree of loyalty that committed teachers have towards their profession is one of their distinguished characters. Generally, teachers who are engaged in their profession and committed to learners and their learning play a crucial role in the development of their learners.

Significant Relationship Between the Organizational Culture and School Custom Practices of Public Elementary School Teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City

Shown in Table 3 is the statistical analysis on the significant relationship between the organizational culture and school custom practices of public elementary school teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City. Based on the analysis, the overall p-value is equal to 0.000 with an r-value equal to 0.730. This means that there is a strong significant positive correlation between the organizational culture and school custom practices of public elementary school teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City. Hence, this study rejects its set null hypothesis. Furthermore, the analysis depicts that an increasing manifestation of organizational culture leads to an increased school custom practices of public elementary school teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City.

Table 3. Significant Relationship Between the Organizational Culture and School Custom Practices of Public Elementary School Teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City

School Custom Practices of Public Elementary School Teachers	Organizational Culture		
	r	p-value	Decision on Ho
Leadership	0.657	0.000	Reject
Teamwork	0.532	0.000	Reject
Adaptability	0.456	0.000	Reject
Overall	0.730	0.000	Reject

Specifically, the analysis in Table 9 highlighted the individual relationship between each indicator of public elementary school teacher’s organizational culture and their school custom practices. Based on the analysis, the Leadership indicator ranked as the top indicator of public elementary school teacher’s organizational culture garnering a strong significant positive correlation with their performance which obtained a p-value of 0.000 and r-value of 0.657. This was followed by the Teamwork indicator obtaining a moderate significant positive correlation with their performance which obtained a p-value of 0.000 and r-value of 0.532. Lastly, is the Adaptability indicator garnering a moderate significant positive correlation with their performance which obtained a p-value of 0.000 and r-value of 0.456. In addition, all of these indicators of public elementary school teacher’s organizational culture show positive direct relationship to their school custom practices in Maa District, Division of Davao City. This means that as the following discussed indicators were

increasingly manifesting by public elementary school teachers then, their school custom practices will also increase.

Regression Analysis of Organizational Culture on the School Custom Practices of Public Elementary School Teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City

As shown in the table 4, the overall analysis obtained p-value of 0.000 and F-value equal to 49.758 stating that there is a significant influence of organizational culture of public elementary school teachers on their school custom practices in Maa District, Division of Davao City. This also implies that the regression model used in the analysis of the study is useful and that there is validity in the interpretation on the assumption of the said influence. Based also on the regression analysis of the study, all of the indicators of public elementary school teacher’s organizational culture significantly influence their school custom practices in Maa District, Division of Davao City.

Specifically, the Leadership indicator of public elementary school teacher’s organizational culture obtained a t-value equal to 7.678 and a p-value equal to 0.000, the Teamwork indicator public elementary school teacher’s organizational culture obtained a t-value equal

to 3.080 and a p-value equal to 0.003, and the Adaptability indicator public elementary school teacher’s organizational culture obtained a t-value equal to 3.337 and a p-value equal to 0.001. With these findings, the set null hypothesis of this study that there are no indica-

Table 4. Regression Analysis of Organizational Culture on the School Custom Practices of Public Elementary School Teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City

School Custom Practices of Public Elementary School Teachers							
Organizational Culture	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
	β	Std. Error	Beta	t			
Constant	.874	.260		3.361	.001		
Leadership	.397	.052	.514	7.678	.000	Reject	Significant
Teamwork	.182	.059	.225	3.080	.003	Reject	Significant
Adaptability	.219	.066	.231	3.337	.001	Reject	Significant

tors of public elementary school teacher’s organizational culture that significantly influence their school custom practices in Maa District, Division of Davao City is rejected. Furthermore, the established results of the regression analysis garnered an R2 equal to 0.563. This means that there are 56.3 percent ascribed to the significance influence of public elementary school teacher’s organizational culture that sig-

nificantly influenced their school custom practices in Maa District, Division of Davao City. Thus, the other 43.7 percent is ascribed to the other indicators not stipulated in the study. Particularly, these indicators could be included to determine that they might have stipulated influence to the school custom practices in Maa District, Division of Davao City.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This section presents the findings of the study based on the data outcome. The conclusions drawn from the findings of the study are likewise outlined in this section. To maximize the significant contribution of this study, the researcher has laid down recommendations in this chapter.

4.1. Findings—This non-experimental research using correlation design in this study aimed to determine the extent of organizational culture and school custom practices of public elementary school teachers. Specifically, this study aimed to determine the extent of organizational culture in terms of leadership, teamwork, and adaptability. Moreover, this also identified the extent of school custom practices of public elementary school teachers in terms of school goals, supportive and caring environment, and curriculum and evaluation. Finally, this study determined the significant relation-

ship between the extent of organizational culture and the extent of school custom practices of public elementary school teachers. Using the non-experimental research, the extent of organizational culture and school custom practices of public elementary school teachers was determined. The respondents of the study were the 120-public elementary school teachers in Maa District, Division of Davao City. A modified teacher-made survey questionnaire was adopted from the study of Organizational Theory of Culture of Schein (1980) as cited by Gudoy (2022) and Theory of Practice of Bourdieu’s as cited

by Andal (2021) was utilized as the main instrument of this study. After thorough analysis, significant findings showed that the extent of organizational culture in terms of leadership, teamwork, and adaptability was high. Similarly, the extent of school custom practices of public elementary school teachers in terms of school goals, supportive and caring environment, and curriculum and evaluation was high which means that it was sometimes manifested while in terms of organizational culture which also high. Hence, the extent of school custom practices as demonstrated by public elementary school teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City was extensive. Finally, indicators of organizational culture such as leadership, teamwork, and adaptability have significant influence of school custom practices of public elementary school teachers.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were offered: The extent of organizational culture of public elementary school teachers was extensive. The extent of school custom practices of public elementary school teachers was also high. There was a strong positive correlation between organizational culture and school custom practices of public elementary school teachers based on the indicators. Based on the results revealed, the following indicators have a strong influence of organizational culture to the school custom practices of public elementary school teachers:

Leadership, Teamwork, and Adaptability.

4.3. Recommendations—The following interventions were offered based on the conclusions of the study: Since the results of the study revealed that the perceived organizational culture and customs are related to the school custom practices, it is recommended that a sustainable organizational culture and application of its practices, implementing the three aspects of organizational culture. For teachers, since the practices of organizational culture of teachers predict the performance of schools when it comes to leadership, teamwork and adaptability, it is recommended secure and sustain better school leadership, management, and governance, participation of teachers is anticipated. As one of the primary pillars of the school-based management, teachers' teamwork and administrator's leadership will not only help but promote the professional and job development of teachers themselves. Future Researchers may this the study investigated the level of perception of teachers when it comes to organizational culture, including the correlation of the aspects to the indicators of customs, it is hereby recommended to use this study as basis and initial reference for a deeper study that can provide a greater causal comparative and inferential link, unlocking other variables and elements that can be identified either through experiment or a mixed method research. A further study is hereby recommended.

5. References

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